

1 **Wound healing and regenerative response mobilization during lineage specification in human**
2 **embryonic development.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here articulation of
9 wound healing and regenerative response program components during lineage commitment in embryonic
10 stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Arwert, E.N., Hoste, E. and Watt, F.M., 2012. Epithelial stem cells, wound healing and cancer.
13 Nature Reviews Cancer, 12(3), pp.170-180.